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“Druggability and Genetic Variability of the ATPase Site and Central Channel of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 Helicase Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

Background:

One of the crucial enzymes in the replication cycle of the SARS-CoV-2 virus is the helicase, which is also known as non-structural protein 13 (nsp13). During the viral life cycle, the holo-RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, also known as nsp12, is thought to coordinate with several additional factors, including the nsp13 helicase (Snijder et al., 2016; Sola et al., 2015) as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. The possible targets for drug development against SARS-CoV-2. Adapted from Habtemariam et al., 2020.

The ATPase domain of nsp13 catalyzes an NTP-dependent unwinding of duplex RNAs into single strands in the 5' to 3' direction. (Habtemariam et al., 2020, Snijder et al., 2016) Previous reports on potent inhibitors targeting the ATPase domain of herpes simplex virus helicase suggest that helicase enzyme is chemically tractable. (Kleymann et al., 2002)

This report provides an overview of the druggability and amino acid variability of both the helicase ATP binding site and its central channel where the RNA molecule binds (figure 2) using the SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase structures available from the protein data bank (PDB).

Figure 2. Nsp13 helicase ATPase site and central channel (PDB: 6zsl). The RNA molecule shown in ribbon diagram from superimposed Upf1 complex (PDB code: 2xz1) and the ADP molecule shown in purple stick representation superimposed from SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase structure bound to ADP (PDB: 6xez).

Methods and Results:

Step 1: Assessing the druggability of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 ATPase site (PDB: 6xez) and central channel with SiteMap

Using SiteMap (Schrodinger, NY) we assessed the druggability of the binding sites using the druggability score (Dscore). The ATP binding site of nsp13 and central channel have Dscores of 1.054 and 1.091 respectively. Both Dscores are indicative of druggable sites.

Figure 3. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase ATPase site. (PDB: 6xez chain F)

Figure 4. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase central channel. (PDB: 6zsl)

Step 2. Determining the residues that line nsp13 helicase ATPase site and central channel.

Using ICM PocketFinder and the nsp13 helicase structure (PDB: 6xez), we identified 38 amino acid sidechains lining the nsp13 ATPase site shown in figure 5: S264, N265, N268, G282, P283, P284, G285, T286, G287, K288, S289, H290, F291, I293, A313, A316, L317, K320, Y324, D374, E375, D401, Q404, L438, G439, T440, C441, R442, R443, Q537, G538, S539, E540, N562, V563, T566, R567, K569.

We conducted a broad survey of viral proteins from Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. By integrating variability and druggability data, we can then infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum viral inhibitors. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses from circulating viral strains in bat reservoir species. We looked at twenty-seven reviewed nsp13 sequences from Uniprot, where six belong to Alphacoronavirus genus entries, and twenty-one belong to the Betacoronavirus genus. We then assessed the variability of amino acid lining the nsp13 helicase ATP binding site and its central channel by performing multiple sequence alignment.

We made diversity dendrograms focusing on the 38 sidechains of the ATPase site (figure 7) and the 25 sidechains of the central channel (figure 8) from step2. In each dendrogram, the consensus profile at each of the sidechains is shown. The colored letters of varying sizes reflect the residues' profile at each amino acid position of interest. The bigger-sized letter is a more commonly found residue at each position.

At the ATPase site, 26 out of 38 residues were found to be identical across these 27 entries which translates to 68% identity, indicating a relatively conserved site. Here are the 9 non-identical residues: S264, N265, N268, T286, F291, A316, Y324, G439, T440, R442, E540, K569.

Figure 7. The diversity dendrogram of helicase ATPase site residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries. Red cross sign indicates non-conserved residues.

At the nsp13 central channel, only 3 out of 25 residues were non-identical; 88% of residues were identical. This shows that nsp13 helicase central channel where the RNA molecule binds is highly conserved.

Figure 8. The diversity dendrogram of helicase central channel residues across 27 Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera UniProt entries. Red cross sign indicates non-conserved residues.

Step 4: Map variations observed among Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries and the variations within only the Betacoronavirus entries onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 crystal structure (PDB: 6zsl).

We mapped the variations shown in step 3 onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 crystal structure. In figure 9 and figure 10 sidechains that are non-identical among the entries at the ATPase site and central channel respectively are highlighted in orange and the conserved sidechains are shown in green.

Figure 9. The genetic variation at nsp13 helicase ATPase site across UniProt entries belonging to Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera mapped onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase Crystal structure (PDB: 6xez). These are the 9 non-identical residues: S264, N265, N268, T286, F291, A316, Y324, G439, T440, R442, E540, K569 which are also shown in the left panel in stick representation.

Figure 10. The genetic variation at nsp13 helicase central channel across UniProt entries belonging to Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera mapped onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase Crystal structure (PDB: 6zsl). These are the 3 non-identical residues among the entries of both Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses: N177, R178, A316. The non-identical residues are also shown in the right panel in stick representation. RNA superimposed from Upf1 complex (PDB: 2xzl) and ADP superimposed from SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase structure bound to ADP (PDB: 6xez).

Step 5: Assessing the genetic variability of ATPase site and central channel of nsp13 among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from Nick Goldman's lab at the European Bioinformatics Institute, looked at more than 39000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients and identified all mutations at the two sites of interest of nsp13 helicase. He identified 12 non-synonymous variants at the ATPase site as shown in table 1 including S264N(1), N268S(4), H290Y(91), H290R(1), F291I(1), I293V(1), Y324H(1), Y324C(1), G439R(1), T440I(1), R442Q(4), S539L(1). For example, at residue number 290, the wild-type sidechain in SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 is histidine. In the sample batch Nicola has looked at, he saw that 39235 samples had histidine at that position while there were 91 with tyrosine at this exact position and one with arginine. In table 1, the source of the variant and its description are noted.

Wildtype Residue	Amino acid variants genome positions of the considered codon position codon	Variant Description
S264	S (39335), N (1) * 17026-17028 a(39337) a(1),g(39336) c(39332),t(5)	5 synonymous variants from USA. Non-synonymous N variant from Canada EPI_ISL_479644.
N268	N (39332), S (4) 17038-17040 a(39336) a(39332),g(4) t(39336)	4 S variants from Sweden
H290	H (39235), R (1), Y (91) 17104-17106 c(39244),t(91) a(39337),g(1) t(39332)	1 R variant from USA EPI_ISL_434084. 91 Y variants from Australia, USA, Morocco, Portugal, Iceland, Scotland, etc, apparently the result of several mutation events (at least 5).
F291	F (39338), I (1) 17107-17109 a(1),t(39338) t(39339) t(39339)	1 I variant from Finland EPI_ISL_481578.
I293	I (39337), V (1) 17113-17115 a(39338),g(1) t(39339) t(39338)	V variant from India EPI_ISL_455757
Y324	Y (39337), H (1), C (2) 17206-17208 c(1),t(39339) a(39338),g(2) t(39340)	2 C variants from Belgium and Switzerland. H variant from Russia EPI_ISL_454732
G439	G (39303), R (1) 17551-17553 a(1),g(39304) g(39305) a(39304)	1 R variant from Scotland EPI_ISL_448196.
T440	T (39293), I (1) 17554-17556 a(39295) c(39294),t(1) c(1),t(39292),g(1)	1 I variant from Scotland EPI_ISL_433567. 1 Codon ACC synonymous variant from Wales EPI_ISL_472775. 1 Codon ACG synonymous variant from USA EPI_ISL_484817.
R442	R (39288), Q (4) 17560-17562 a(1),c(39294) a(4),g(39291) a(1),t(9),g(39282)	1 Codon AGG synonymous variant from Singapore EPI_ISL_462423. 4 codon CAG Q variants from India, Switzerland, England and Wales. 1 Codon CGA synonymous variant from Finland EPI_ISL_481596. 9 synonymous codon CGT variants from USA, Belgium, Israel, Sweden, Australia.
S539	S (39334), L (1) 17851-17853 t(39336) c(39336),t(1) a(39337),g(1)	L variant from England EPI_ISL_466203. Synonymous variant from England EPI_ISL_440612

Table 1. Amino acid sidechains of helicase ATPase Site with non-synonymous variants identified across over 39000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients. *The non-synonymous variants are highlighted in bold font.

For example, at amino acid position H290 of the ATPase site, there are one R variant and 91 Y variants. We map the SARS-CoV-2 variants onto nsp13 helicase crystal structure as shown in figure 11.

Figure 11. Mapping the non-synonymous variants found in SARS-CoV-2 samples onto nsp13 crystal structure. (PDB: 6xez chain F). The H290 position corresponding to H290Y(91) and H290R(1) is shown in orange and the remaining amino acid positions corresponding to the rest of non-synonymous variants are shown in gold which include: S264N(1), N268S(4), F291I(1), I293V(1), Y324H(1), Y324C(1), G439R(1), T440I(1), R442Q(4), S539L(1).

In contrast to the ATPase site of nsp13 helicase, where there were many non-synonymous variants identified, Nicola De Maio identified zero non-synonymous variants at the central channel of nsp13 helicase across 39000 sequence samples. This finding speaks to the high conservation of the RNA binding site of nsp13. He did identify a stop-codon, as shown in table 2. At this point, it is unclear whether this is due to a sequencing error.

Wildtype Residue	Amino acid variants genome positions of the considered codon position codon	Variant Description
R178	R (39338), *(1) 16768-16770 c(39338),t(1) g(39339) a(39339)	Stop codon from Scotland, EPI_ISL_449265

Table 2. Amino acid sidechains of helicase central channel with non-synonymous variants identified across over 39000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients.

**Nonsense mutation due to stop codon (tga).

Conclusion:

We conclude that the ATPase site of SARS-CoV-2 nsp13 helicase is less conserved than its RNA-binding central channel across Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses. We observe a similar pattern by looking at non-synonymous variants across SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients where

the ATPase site had 12 non-synonymous variants while the central channel had none. While the ATPase site where ADP binds is druggable and relatively conserved (%68), the central channel of nsp13 helicase where RNA binds is druggable and highly conserved (88%). Our finding supports the design of pan-coronavirus inhibitors targeting the central channel of nsp13 helicase.

References

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